

A STUDY ON TRIMODAL DEPENDENCY GRAPH FOR SOFTWARE CLUSTERING

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ABSTRACT- Software clustering is the process of combining multiple systems or applications into a cluster that act as a single system. The subsystems are reverse engineered to extract design data. When large software systems are reverse engineered there is possibility of the system decomposition hierarchy. The Bunch's software clustering tool shows how meta-heuristic search algorithms can be applied to the software clustering problem, successfully. But some uncertainty prevails whether Bunch provides optimal solution. The optimal solution for trivial systems may be achieved using an exhaustive search. Hence a clustering of software modules method with single graph is used in the existing method to obtain optimal solution by low coupling and high cohesion criterion. The advantage of using spectral methods is that the results this technique produced are within a known factor of the optimal solution. But the spectral single graph shows all the clusters in a single MDG which is complex and costly to maintain. The single graph view shows every system as a node which enables further complex cluster views. This study proposes a method called clustering of software modules with multiple graph views which improves the optimal efficiency and reduces the complexity. In this study the usage of multiple graphs for separate systems also reduces the maintenance cost to a greater extent.

1. INTRODUCTION ABOUT SOFTWARE CLUSTERING

Software clustering is a method of turning multiple computer servers into a cluster which is a group of servers that acts like a single system. Clustering software is installed in each of the servers in the group. Each of the servers maintains the same information and collectively they perform administrative tasks such as load balancing, determining node failures, and assigning failover duty. The other clustering method, hardware clustering, requires that specialized hardware be installed in a single server that

Controls the cluster. Because servers can easily be added or removed from the cluster as needs dictate, a software cluster is more scalable than its hardware-based counterpart. Furthermore, because it doesn't require specialized hardware, a

Typical cluster models include:

- Connectivity models: for example hierarchical clustering builds models based on distance connectivity.

- Centroids models: for example the k-means algorithm represents each cluster by a single mean vector.
- Distribution models: clusters are modeled using statistical distributions, such as multivariate normal distributions used by the Expectation-maximization algorithm.
- Density models: for example DBSCAN and OPTICS defines clusters as connected dense regions in the data space.
- Subspace models: in Bi-clustering (also known as Co-clustering or two-mode-clustering), clusters are modeled with both cluster members and relevant attributes.
- Group models: some algorithms do not provide a refined model for their results and just provide the grouping information.
- Graph-based models: a clique, i.e., a subset of nodes in a graph such that every two nodes in the subset are connected by an edge can be considered as a prototypical form of cluster. Relaxations of the complete connectivity requirement a fraction of the edges can be missing are known as quasi-cliques.

inside a building are interconnected which are further connected to the servers of the next building. The common fiber channel disk arrays are shared between the systems of the two buildings through the routers and the Ethernet cables which connect all the servers into cluster acting as a single system with many users.

2. BUNCH SOFTWARE CLUSTERING TOOL ALGORITHM

The Bunch tool implements a variety of meta-heuristic search algorithms to cluster graphs. Bunch’s hill-climbing clustering algorithm starts by generating a random partition of the MDG. Modules from this partition are then rearranged systematically in an attempt to find an “improved” partition. If a better partition is found, the process iterates, using the improved partition as the basis for finding even better partitions. The hill-climbing search algorithm eventually converges when no improved partitions of the MDG can be found.

The Bunch genetic algorithm (GA) uses operators such as selection, crossover, and mutation to determine a “good” partition of the MDG. This technique is especially good at finding solutions quickly, but we have found that the quality of the results produced by Bunch’s hill-climbing algorithms is typically better. Although each of Bunch’s search algorithms works differently, they all examine partitions from the very large search space of MDG partitions. Note that the number of MDG partitions, the Bell number, is $O(N!)$, where N is the number of modules in the MDG. Thus, Bunch’s search algorithms require a way to determine if one MDG partition is “better” than another. To address this need we define an objective function, which is called as Modularization Quality (MQ), to evaluate the relative quality of MDG

1.2 Architecture of Software Clustering

Figure 1- Cluster site 1 and Cluster site 2

This architectural model considers two buildings where the clustering of the servers

partitions. The MQ function works by calculating a value which is called as the Cluster Factor (CF) for each cluster. Given an MDG partitioned into k clusters, MQ is calculated by summing CF for each cluster of the partitioned MDG. CF_i for cluster i ($1 \leq i \leq k$) is defined as a normalized ratio between the total weight of the internal edges (edges within the cluster) and half of the total weight of external edges. The weight of the external edges is split in half in order to apply an equal penalty to both clusters that are connected by an external edge. We refer to the internal edges of a cluster as intra-edges, and the edges between two distinct clusters i and j as inter-edges. If edge weights are not provided by the MDG, we assume that each edge has a weight of 1. The MQ measurement design is based on the assumption that good software systems consist of a set of highly-cohesive subsystems clusters in the MDG that are loosely coupled together.

The clustering problem, as solved by Bunch, can be stated as a good partition of an MDG graph. We use the term partition in the traditional mathematical sense, that is, the decomposition of a set of elements such as all nodes of a graph into mutually disjoint clusters. By a "good partition" we mean a partition where highly interdependent modules (nodes) are grouped in the same subsystems and, conversely, independent modules are assigned to separate subsystems. Finding a good graph partition involves systematically navigating through a very large search space of all possible partitions for that graph. Bunch treats graph partitioning or clustering as an optimization problem. The goal of the optimization is to maximize the value of an objective function, called Modularization Quality (MQ). MQ determines the quality of

an MDG partition quantitatively as the trade between interconnectivity (i.e., dependencies between the modules of two distinct subsystems) and intra-connectivity (i.e., dependencies between the modules of the same subsystem). This trade is based on the assumption that well-designed software systems are organized into cohesive subsystems that are loosely interconnected. Hence, MQ is designed to reward the creation of highly cohesive clusters, and to penalize excessive coupling between clusters. All values of MQ are between -1 (no internal cohesion) and +1 (no external coupling). This algorithm is not practical for MDGs with a large number of modules, because the number of partitions of a graph grows exponentially with respect to its number of nodes. Thus, Bunch uses more efficient search algorithms to discover acceptable sub-optimal results. These algorithms are based on hill-climbing and genetic algorithms.

3. CLUSTERING OF SOFTWARE MODULES ALGORITHM WITH A SINGLE GRAPH

Clustering of software modules is a general framework for partitioning the rows and columns of matrices derived from the data in terms of few of their eigenvectors. In most cases the clustering problem will be related to a variation of cuts in graphs, and the spectral method will be an underlying technique for the approximation of graph partition problems. This measure is defined as the proportion of the total cut-link weight, normalized by the sizes of the partitions. Given the MDG of a software system, the search for a good partition of the MDG is done. This is accomplished by treating clustering as an optimization problem where the goal is to maximize the value of an

objective function. This objective function characterizes the trade-off between coupling (i.e., connections between the components of two distinct clusters) and cohesion (i.e., connections between the components of the same cluster). Software is almost always designed with this tradeoff in mind. For example, the structure of a compiler is typically a simple pipeline of compilation phases, where each phase is implemented as a complex set of lower-level software components. The objective function will cluster the structure of software to recover the architecture of the system. Specifically, the objective function is designed to identify the set of complex components that constitute individual software capabilities as well as to identify how these components interact with other complex components in the rest of the system.

Clustering of software modules approach naturally generalizes the spectral undirected graph clustering scheme. An undirected graph is a special case of a directed graph, that is, an edge of an undirected graph connecting vertex u to vertex v represents two directed edges, one from u to v ; and the other from v to u : The issue of spectral directed graph clustering has attracted a lot of research interest, in particular, in the web search engine community. Compared with other directed graph clustering techniques, the key insight in the approach is to regard a directed graph as a Markov chain. Their approach is built on random walks over a directed graph rather than directly manipulating the combinatorial structures of the directed graph. It is worth noting that there is a wide choice of random walks given a directed graph, and different random walk choices generally lead to different clustering results.

$$C(P_k) = \sum_{1 \leq i \leq k} \frac{\text{vol } \partial V_i}{\text{vol } V_i}$$

Where, V_i is the k - partition of the graph.

4. CLUSTERING OF SOFTWARE MODULES ALGORITHM WITH MULTIPLE GRAPHS

A natural approach to Clustering of software modules with multi-view learning is to define a kernel for each type of data representation, and then combine those kernels. In web categorization, the kernel for the link graph can be defined as the co-link matrix, in which two web pages have a co-link if a third web page points to both of them. In the kernel for text, each entry can be given by the inner product between the corresponding document vectors. If the multiple views are represented by different graphs, the inverse of the graph Laplacian can be regarded as a Kernel and, consequently, one may convexly combine graph Laplacians. The underlying principle of this methodology is unclear however. It is well-known that the clustering of software modules approach for a single graph is derived from a real-valued relaxation of the combinatorial normalized cut which naturally leads to the graph Laplacian but any literature addressing the issue of which combinatorial cut can lead to the convex combination of graph Laplacians in the situation of multiple graphs. The basic motivation of defining such a multiple graph cut is that we want to obtain a cut which is good on average while it may not be the best for a single graph. The parameter α is used to specify the relative importance of each graph in clustering. It is not hard to imagine that the relative importance measure varies across different clustering goals.

$$L_f = \lambda \Pi f$$

The multiple graph cut can be understood as follows:

Assume a random walk with the current position being at a vertex in one graph. Then, in the next step, the walker may continue his random walk in the same graph with a certain probability, or jump to the other graph with the remaining probability and continue his random walk there. A subset of vertices is regarded as a cluster if during the random walk the probability of leaving this subset is small while the stationary probability mass of the same subset is large. It is obvious how to extend the above analysis to more than two graphs. Finally, the multiple graphs clustering of software modules are summarized.

$$c(S) = \frac{mvol \partial S (mvol S + mvol S^c)}{mvol S mvol S^c}$$

5. COMPARABILITY OF SOFTWARE CLUSTERING ALGORITHMS

Evaluation of software clustering algorithms is typically done by comparing the clustering results to an authoritative decomposition prepared manually by a system expert. A well-known drawback of this approach is the fact that there are many, equally valid ways to decompose a software system, since different clustering objectives create different decompositions. Evaluating all clustering algorithms against a single authoritative decomposition can lead to biased results.

The various software clustering algorithms published in the literature have different clustering objectives, i.e. assumptions on what constitutes a meaningful

decomposition of a software system. This leads to clustering results that, while significantly different from each other, offer equally valid points of view on the system's high level structure. Evaluating such clustering results by comparing them to a single authoritative decomposition, that may or may not have been created with the same clustering objective in mind, can lead to significantly biased results. For this reason, we define that two clustering algorithms that produce significantly different results are not comparable, i.e. they should not be compared against the same authoritative decomposition since the obtained results will be meaningless if not misleading. Conversely, we define two clustering algorithms to be comparable when they produce similar results. Comparable algorithms can be compared using an authoritative decomposition. We quantify what is meant by "similar clustering results". In order to do so, we require a large number of module dependency graphs (MDGs) extracted from software systems. Since this is impractical to do, we utilized an approach that generates simulated MDGs.

Two algorithms are considered to be non-comparable if they produce significantly different results across a variety of software systems. More precisely, we define those two algorithms are non-comparable if in the majority of cases they produce results that are more different than similar, i.e. the similarity is less than 50%. If the above does not hold, then the algorithms are considered comparable. This definition may appear biased towards making algorithms look comparable, since one could have used only the average in the definition. However, even with this definition most major algorithms are shown to be non-comparable. The findings

illustrate an important benefit of assessing algorithm comparability. One may be able to deduce properties of an algorithm they are considering for a software clustering task by studying the properties of comparable, well-known algorithms.

6. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

Finally in this module the performance of the existing and the proposed approaches were illustrated and evaluated. In the existing method the meta-heuristic and clustering of software modules with single graph is used. In the proposed system the clustering of software modules with multiple graphs is used to reduce complexity. Compare to existing system the proposed graph is simple and also the maintenance cost is reduced in the proposed system.

Figure 2- Guess Visualization of clustering of software modules with multiple views

6.1 Comparison graph

Figure 3- Comparison of Existing and Proposed Systems

The comparison graph shows the bunch analysis between the existing method and the proposed system. The number of clusters used is taken along the x-axis. The bunch optimal level is taken along the y-axis. Comparing both the methods the existing method reaches a bunch level which is far from the optimal solution. The proposed system achieves higher bunch level which is near perfect the global optimal solution. Initially the existing method leaps to achieve perfect solution but as the no of clusters increases the bunch level falls short by a greater margin and retards in obtaining solution. The fall of bunch level in the existing method implies the fact that it is suitable only for the systems with small number of clusters. Hence the newly proposed clustering of software modules with multiple graphs is used which achieves the near perfect optimal solution. Though initially retarding, it achieves global solution as the clusters increases.

CONCLUSION

The clustering algorithms are used to simplify the server applications into smaller clusters to enable higher efficiency denoted by

the optimal global solution. The existing method of bunch clustering tool uses the meta-heuristic approach to analyze the functioning of the clusters which is called as spectral clustering. The spectral clustering uses a single graph view which is greatly efficient for small no of clusters. But when the number of clusters in the system increases the graph becomes complex thus affecting the optimal solution. This approach requires separate partitioning methods to simplify the view but still the system could not attain optimum solution. The lack of a global solution makes the clusters to be more time consuming and thus the performance degrades. As the result of this, the maintenance cost also increases. Hence the enhanced method should be implemented. Clustering of software modules method is used to overcome the short comings of the meta-heuristic search algorithm. The clustering of software modules initially uses the single graph view model which provides global solution compared to the Bunch software clustering. But due to the usage of single graph to analyze an entire cluster the system lacks simplicity and causes high maintenance cost. Hence the clustering of software modules with multiple graph view model is introduced which partitions the single complex graph into smaller multiple graphs. Thus the multiple view method reduces complexity as well as maintenance cost to a greater extent compared to the existing model.

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